

INTERPRETATION OF THE TOURISM TERMS IN THE POINT OF LEXICOGRAPHICS

Yoqubov Odil

*Researcher of Tashkent State University of Economics,
EFL Instructor of "TIAME" National Research University*

Abstract. Theoretical lexicography studies the history of lexicography, types of dictionaries, requirements for dictionaries, critical analysis of existing dictionaries, practical lexicography deals with the study, collection, improvement and consumption of a particular word group. Practical lexicography involves the application of general theoretical foundations and rules of lexicography in the process of creating a dictionary.

Keywords: lexicography, tourism terms, bilingual dictionary, a language dictionary, lexicographer, equivalent

INTRODUCTION

Consensus on the essence of the term lexicography and its recognition as a science is also a relatively recent phenomenon in linguistics. Lexicography consists of theoretical and practical sections that coexist and function in harmony with each other. While theoretical lexicography studies the history of lexicography, types of dictionaries, requirements for dictionaries, critical analysis of existing dictionaries, practical lexicography deals with the study, compilation, improvement and consumption of a certain type of vocabulary. Practical lexicography involves the application of general theoretical principles and rules of lexicography in the process of creating a dictionary. Lexicography is still a very young field of science, and researches in this field are not enough in comparison with other branches of linguistics. According to famous lexicographer L. Zgust, there are only twenty significant works on lexicography in the world lexicographic community.

Dictionaries have long been designed not only to provide information related to the translation or use of a particular word, but also to expand people's intercultural secular knowledge. Although it is known that the culture of different peoples contributes to the formation of tourism terms as a separate terminological system of the field, encyclopedic information about these cultures and the etymology of related terms remains an integral part of special dictionaries. It also serves to fully understand the content of the text, the mood in it and the concept of «text culture». The lexicography of terms has become a subject of particular interest. This is evidenced by the works of the first President of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov: "High spirituality is invincible" [2008; 87]. Especially in such important areas as fundamental sciences, modern communication and information technologies, banking and financial systems, the use of our language, etymological and comparative dictionaries. There is no doubt that the development of the necessary terms and expressions, concepts and categories, in a word, the all-round development of the Uzbek language on a scientific basis will serve such noble goals as the awareness of national identity, a sense of homeland. There are basically two types of dictionaries: encyclopedic and philological [2002; 82]. Terminological dictionaries, which are the subject of our research, are part of specialized dictionaries, which are a smaller section of philological dictionaries. Special dictionaries can take the form of both annotated (i.e. monolingual) and translated (i.e., at least bilingual) dictionaries related to a specific field (specialty) of science and technology. The task of terminological dictionaries is to interpret terms of a specific area and to clarify their content. They serve as the basis for the required field. For this reason, such dictionaries are also called «dictionaries of some industries» [2006; 56]. The history of the tradition of creating a dictionary in our country begins with the Devon lug'atit Turk of the 11th century in Kashgari. Since then, many dictionaries have been created: "Mukaddammatul Adab" (The Fourth Language Dictionary of the XII century), «At-tukhfatuz zakiyati fil-lug'atit-turkia» (XIII century), Badoe-ul-lug'at (15th century), Abushka (16th century), Kelurnoma (17th century), Muntahab ul-lug'at (18th

century), Sanglo (18th century), «Dictionary of the Chigaty and Ottoman Turks»(XIX century), «Comparative Dictionary of TürkoTatar Dialects», «Experience of the Turkic dialect», «Russian-Sart and Sart-Russian dictionary» (1884-1912), Concise Russian-Uzbek Dictionary (2006), «The Perfect Russian-Uzbek Dictionary» (1927- 28), Concise Uzbek-Russian Dictionary (2007), Uzbek-Russian Dictionary (1931), «Russian-Uzbek complete dictionary» (1934), «Concise Uzbek-Russian Dictionary» (1935), Russian-Uzbek Dictionary (1942). However, the creation of terminological dictionaries belongs to a new era – the second half of the twentieth century [1992; 113]. From the point of view of world statistics, dictionaries were compiled four thousand years ago to explain certain religious concepts, giving an idea of the religions that existed in the Middle East, they are considered the first specialized dictionaries [1995; 10]. Decades ago, just by looking at the ability to collect existing words and put them into a collection, the complexity and responsibility of lexicography that was incorporated into technical specialties could be seen from a small number of high functional value vocabularies in practice. Lexicography is an interdisciplinary science.

METHODS

Achievements of science and technology, as well as the development of the socio-political and economic life of countries require a constant expansion of the vocabulary of languages, the addition of new lexical units and obsolescence of obsolete ones. Sometimes new units enter the dictionary under the new name of an existing concept. E.A. Zemskaya points out how difficult it is to learn new words when they are not associated with old ones, and that the relationship of words in a language is a reflection of the relationship between the real object of existence and events. Thus, the finalization and regulation of terminology in each area remains one of the urgent problems of modern lexicography. The fact that terminological systems are free from confusion, clearly and systematized is a factor that determines the culture, spirituality and literacy of a country. However, the lexicography of terms is a

relatively young aspect of theoretical and practical lexicography, and it still has many problems. 1. The first problem is associated with the ambiguity of terms, which is found in the terminological system of all industries. In fact, terms should clearly express the nature of the concept in a particular area, and its scope should be limited to that area only. Their important feature is that they are unambiguous in nature and do not have emotionally expressive associations, which distinguishes them from ordinary words. Indeed, the lexical meaning of the terms also requires this (the term comes from the Latin word *terminus*, meaning «border», «boundary marker», «restriction» [2006; 50]. 2. The second urgent problem is the meaning of terms. This leads to the abstraction and confusion associated with their consumption. In fact, the development of society requires that one of the significant options be excluded from the dictionary in the course of sociocultural selection. In this case, an option falls out of consumption that does not accurately express the content of the concept it expresses or causes inconvenience in the application (due to the fact that it consists of graphics, a sound shell, a large number of components). But this will take time. For this reason, terminological dictionaries are constantly being updated and refined. 3. The next problem arises due to the fact that a specific term does not fully correspond to the essence of the concept it represents. The reason is to consider the translation of terms from a foreign language as an artificial and technical process, and not to be creative. As a result, the term loses its functional value and is depreciated. The scope of the terms introduced should be limited, clear and understandable and applied consistently in this voluntary context. 4. The next drawback is associated with the excessive length (more precisely, multicomponent) terms. Compactness and ease of use are critical for terminology units. “In such artificial conditions, first of all, the economy of speech is disturbed, which, in turn, negatively affects thinking. Secondly, the probability of an elliptical phenomenon (loss of speech elements) increases” [2006; 56]. Speaking in particular about the Uzbek language, the peculiarities of our language often require the translation of a one-component term from a foreign language as a combination of two or more components. For this reason, when

developing terminological systems, it is very important to achieve maximum conciseness by critically approaching this process, without resorting to blind translation and using the rich internal capabilities of our language. In general, the formation of compound terms using the syntactic method is one of the most effective methods in any language, as evidenced by the fact that in any terminological system there are more compound terms than single-component terms. In fact, according to the universal opinion existing in linguistics, one-component terms are considered basic terms, and many other terms are derived from them (For example, tourism → tourism industry → green tourism, etc.).

RESULTS

The micro-composition problems of a special dictionary are associated with the choice of lexicographic details of the actual dictionary entry. A comparative study of terminological dictionaries in the tourism sector showed that the lexicographic details used in these dictionaries can be divided into several groups. However, it should be noted that for Russian tourist terminology, this parameter, in our opinion, is quite important, since there are many borrowings among the terms of the tourism sector that are not fully assimilated by the language. Various grammatical information about the term can also be attributed to formal requisites. All analyzed Uzbek dictionaries lack such information. In some English-language publications, the term's part of speech and irregular forms of inflection are given. The formal group also includes information about phonetic, graphic, morphological and syntactic variants, as well as information about short or full variants of the term. Almost all English-language dictionaries reflect graphic options related to area affiliation (British, American versions, for example, traveler – US traveler) and short/full options (health tourism – health-care tourism). Some Russian-language dictionaries, in turn, give only short and complete forms of terms, for example, tourist agent – travel agent. However, the Russian terminology of tourism has a fairly large number of variants which, in our opinion, should be reflected in dictionaries. → specialists (developers of tourism

statistics, i.e. experts involved in the implementation, editing and monitoring of tourism conditions, developers of tourism services and products) → semi-professionals (tour operators, travel agents and guides; tourism promotion representatives) → students (potential tourists and students studying at specialized universities) → intermediaries (intermediate group members such as translators, journalists and writers) In sociolinguistic terms, scientific or technical terms are words that belong to a specific group of scientists or a community of experts. Since tourism is a sector of the economy and the production of goods and services, it would undoubtedly be advisable to include the terminological system of tourism in the second group of terms. It is very important for a lexicographer to work with a specialist in the field from the beginning to the end of the terminology system development process [2007; 29]. There are good reasons for this. When developing a dictionary of common words, the lexicographer himself can easily provide accurate and detailed explanations of words, as well as develop examples of authorship. To explain specific terms and understand the situations in which they are used, the lexicographer must have not only linguistic knowledge, but also an understanding of this specific area. The second reason is that the rapid development of corpus linguistics in the new century made it possible to quote examples in general-purpose dictionaries, to embody words in their real context. Indeed, lexicographers can now create dictionaries that perform a truly communicative function, summarizing the most commonly used contexts of lexical units using a ready-made language corpus. But there is no such possibility for terminology yet. This is due to the fact that the language used by corporations is not adapted to work with words within a specific use [1988; 366]. The creation of a special linguistic corpus for scientific and technical terms is observed by leading modern linguists used dictionaries consist of the following typical macro-structural elements: – Contents – Introduction – Organizations and individuals who work together and contribute to the creation of the vocabulary – Covered Territory Names – Operating instructions – Dictionary section – Applications Specialists and organizations involved in the creation of a special

dictionary should be reflected in the macrostructure of the dictionary. While for general dictionaries it is enough to turn to one specialist, the creation of improved terminological dictionaries requires the help of dozens of specialists [2016; 400]. However, if the dictionary is a concise part of the introductory part in general dictionaries, it must be given separately in special dictionaries and contain all the necessary information (target user, direction of a field or subsector in the dictionary, how much information can be found about entered terms, order of terms [2016; 399] should be covered in the form of detailed comments on this information and it is of great importance, especially if a special dictionary is being created for several groups of consumers. The macrostructure of monolingual and bilingual specialized dictionaries may consist of practically the same information representation, but their microstructure obeys different principles.

DISCUSSIONS

Bilingual special dictionaries can be one-way or two-way. There are translated equivalents of the list of terms given in one-way dictionaries as a result of only one-way transformation (either from English to Uzbek, or from Uzbek to English). Most modern terminology dictionaries are one-way [1995; 52] Bilingual special dictionaries have a wider set of functions, and thanks to a two-way transformation, they can be used to understand information both in foreign special contexts and to provide new information, i.e. they are designed for both receptive and productive language practice. This can make them larger and more awkward to use in practice. Some scholars disapprove of them because of these aspects [2007; 76]. Grammatical information about lemmas is also an integral part of the microstructure of each vocabulary. According to a standard lexical practice, grammatical information should be provided with each quoted lemma. However, this situation depends on the type of a dictionary. The above rule applies to monolingual dictionaries. In bilingual dictionaries, it is permissible to provide grammatical information with equivalents. Indeed, the user's ability to correctly apply equivalents in practice is the goal of this

type of dictionaries. The grammatical information provides the necessary explanation of the category, morphology and syntactic features of lexical units. Initially, it is important that the word series is presented.

CONCLUSION

The nature of the dictionary is determined by how the elements of the microstructure of the dictionary is presented. This requires the lexicographer to put himself/herself in the shoes of a potential dictionary user, get a feel for the intricacies of the application, and act accordingly. For example, the citation of transcription elements differs depending on the type of active and inactive vocabulary. In passive dictionaries, the primary goal of the user is to understand a spoken or a written text. Naturally, the content of the lexical unit is of paramount importance here. The user finds a word in the dictionary, selects one of the existing values that matches the context of the target, and interprets the information in the text. In this process, the pronunciation and grammatical information of the word does not matter much. Indeed, information about its category and syntactic features can also be learned through other words in the context in which it interacts.

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